

Achieving activated sludge granulation and evaluating the performance of an innovative anaerobic-anoxic sequencing batch reactor system

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Abstract

Granular sludge (GS) technology is a cutting-edge advancement in wastewater (WW) treatment, enabling the simultaneous removal of carbon (C), nitrogen (N), and phosphorus (P) in a single reactor. The process relies on granular microbial aggregates that support the growth of different communities, including nitrifiers, heterotrophic bacteria, polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (PAOs), and glycogen-accumulating organisms (GAOs). The granules enhance pollutant removal through spatially distinct metabolic activities, and PAOs play a key role in P removal by storing it intracellularly as polyphosphate, allowing P to be removed from WW and recovered.

This study investigates the operation of an anaerobic-anoxic sequencing batch reactor (SBR) system fed on acetate as C source using nitrate as the sole electron acceptor. Operating in 4-hour cycles, divided into 90-min anaerobic and 150-min anoxic phases, the system promoted biomass granulation, developing dense granules from conventional flocculent sludge.

Experimental results demonstrated the effective removal of organics, nitrate, and P, with low P release-to-C uptake ratio and high specific P uptake. The system also achieved excellent sludge settleability (SVI equal to 85.4 mL/g TSS after 5 minutes), minimal solids discharge (12 ± 8 mg TSS/L), and high-quality effluent, demonstrating that anoxic granular sludge technology could be a sustainable solution for advanced WW treatment and nutrient recovery in case of appropriate WW composition.

Keywords

Denitrifying biological process, Granular sludge, Phosphorous removal, Polyphosphate-accumulating organisms, Wastewater treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Phosphorus (P) is essential for ecosystems and agriculture but can cause eutrophication when excessively discharged in water bodies (Schindler et al., 2008). Wastewater (WW) treatment plants conventionally remove P using chemical methods, though this process becomes increasingly inefficient and costly at low P concentrations in influent water, requiring high chemical dosage and increasing environmental impacts (Kroiss et al., 2011).

Biological P removal using polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (PAOs), provides a more sustainable and cost-effective alternative. PAOs can simultaneously remove P and organic pollutants from WW under alternating anaerobic and aerobic conditions (Zhao et al., 2022). Specific strains of PAOs can also use nitrite and nitrate as electron acceptors, enabling simultaneous nitrogen (N) removal via denitrification, reducing the need for energy-intensive aeration and minimizes sludge production (Wu et al., 2023).

Among existing biological processes, granular sludge (GS), with its better settling characteristics and stress resilience, is particularly suitable for enriching denitrifying PAOs and offers the opportunity for improved P and N removal (Purba et al., 2020).

This study aimed to develop granular sludge under strict anoxic conditions (later referred to as anoxic granular sludge, AnoxGS) from conventional flocculant sludge in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR) operated under alternating anaerobic/anoxic conditions. In the present research work the long-term proof-of-concept of an AnoxGS system at lab-scale fed with synthetic WW is demonstrated and the system performance in the removal of organics and nutrients as well as in the flocculant sludge conversion into high-density granules are evaluated, in the view of assessing its potential as effective and sustainable WW treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Flocculant sludge from a conventional WWTP was inoculated in a 5-L lab-scale SBR, operated at constant volume for over 280 days fed by synthetic WW. The treatment process was structured on 4-h cycles, consisting of 90-min anaerobic and 150-min anoxic phases. Each phase included three subphases: simultaneous feeding and discharging, followed by a mixing phase, and concluded with a fast-settling phase of 10 minutes. The reactor was designed for simultaneous bottom feeding and top effluent discharge to optimize hydraulic conditions for granulation.

During the cycle, two different streams were prepared in tap water and fed to the reactor, with a volume exchange ratio of 40%: (i) primarily, at the beginning of the anaerobic phase, a stream rich in organic carbon (C) as sodium acetate, ammonia, and phosphate was fed, (ii) then, at the beginning of the anoxic phase, another stream enriched with nitrate and phosphate was fed. The detailed composition of the synthetic WW streams fed to the SBR over the experimental activity is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of synthetic WW streams (avg. \pm st.dev.).

Component	Concentration in WW [mg/L]	
	Anaerobic phase	Anoxic phase
Sodium acetate (as COD)	150.5 \pm 21.8	-
Ammonium (as N-NH ₄ ⁺)	26.6 \pm 3.5	-
Phosphorus (as P-PO ₄ ³⁻)	10.5 \pm 1.8	13.2 \pm 2.6
Nitrate (as N-NO ₃ ⁻)	8.2 \pm 1.0	26.1 \pm 3.5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Granular sludge formation and settleability

At the end of the experimental activity, AnoxGS exhibited excellent settleability, with sludge volume index (SVI) at 5 minutes lower than 100 mL/g TSS and SVI₃₀/SVI₅ ratio of 0.8. The solids concentration in the mixed liquor increased from 1.4 to 2.5 g VSS/L, although the volatile suspended solids over total suspended solids ratio consistently decreased to 52% (Figure 1).

After starting periodical sludge extraction to control the average sludge retention time, maintained at 29 \pm 8 days, the solids ratio gradually stabilized between 50-55%, ashowing a slight increase during the final phase. Concurrently, the formation of granular sludge was observed, with the concentration of granules (diameter > 200 μ m) increasing from 1.4 to 1.9 g VSS/L in the mixed liquor. Figure 2 shows the transformation of the biomass from suspended flocculant sludge, characterized by its filamentous structure, into denser and round granules, which took place in approximately 15 weeks. By the end of the experimental activity, most of the granules measured between 200-500 μ m in diameter, with some aggregates reaching up to 700 μ m.

Removal of organics and nutrients

The system showed outstanding removal efficiencies for organic C and nitrate, achieving removal efficiencies of 74 \pm 12% and 84 \pm 17%, respectively (Figure 3). Regarding P, AnoxGS reached removal efficiency of 23 \pm 18%. Although these results are remarkable, particularly when compared with conventional activated sludge systems, they may be constrained by the low-strength WW tested, which limits concentration gradients within the granules, essential for an effective substrate diffusion into the granules. Furthermore, an imbalanced C:N:P ratio may partially restrict the metabolic potential of denitrifying PAOs and other denitrifying consortia. However, the relatively low effluent concentrations achieved demonstrate that, under more favorable conditions, AnoxGS could emerge as a viable alternative for next-generation wastewater treatment.

By the end of experimental activity, the specific denitrification activity of AnoxGS peaked at 3 mg

N-NO_3^- ($\text{g VSS}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)⁻¹. Additionally, the AnoxGS process exhibited excellent P uptake capacity, achieving a specific P uptake rate of $1.9 \text{ mg P-PO}_4^{3-}$ ($\text{g VSS}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$)⁻¹ during the anoxic phase.

Figure 1. Evolution in the SBR during the experimental activity of (a) TSS, VSS and VSS/TSS ratio in the SBR, and (b), and SVI₅, SVI₃₀ and SVI₅/SVI₃₀ ratio.

Figure 2. Evolution of sludge structure from flocs inoculum (left) to GS (right) in 15 weeks.

Figure 3. Trends of influent (a) and effluent (b) sCOD, N-NO₃⁻, and P-PO₄³⁻ concentrations during the experimental period.

Phosphorus recovery by granules

Once stable conditions were reached, AnoxGS demonstrated an excellent capacity of C storage and P recovery, exhibiting a P release to C uptake ratio of 0.15 mol P/mol C. This value is significantly lower than the stoichiometric ratio of 0.5 reported in the literature (Henze et al., 2008). During the anoxic phase, the granules were highly efficient in recovering the phosphate released during the anaerobic phase, achieving a P uptake-to-release ratio of 3.6.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides the first results of successful cultivation and operation of AnoxGS under controlled working conditions. The present research work demonstrates the following key findings:

- GS can successfully be cultivated under strictly anaerobic-anoxic conditions;
- Under steady-state conditions, the AnoxGS process can effectively remove organic C and nutrients from synthetic WW without the use of free dissolved oxygen and with reduced sludge production.

The novelty of this work lies in demonstrating the adaptability of GS to non-aerobic environments, offering insights for the development of innovative and sustainable WW treatment strategies.

Future research will focus on evaluating the treatment performance and the granule behavior under more challenging operating conditions, such as higher volume exchange ratios, use of real WW as influent, and variable organic loads and composition. This will support the development of a complete and sustainable treatment concept, marking AnoxGS as a robust technology for next-generation WW biotreatments.

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